

Prognostic Value of NT-Pro-BNP and Serum Magnesium in Acute Exacerbations of COPD: A Comprehensive Clinical StudyAyachit Kesharwani¹, Vasu Hariranjana Patoudi², Priya Sasmal³, Neha Vishwakarma^{2*}¹MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India
²MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India³MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, Nil Ratan Sarkar Medical College, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Neha Vishwakarma

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Abstract:**Background:** Acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (AECOPD) are significant events that can lead to increased hospitalizations, healthcare costs, and mortality. NT-Pro-BNP, a biomarker of cardiac stress, and serum magnesium levels have been associated with COPD exacerbations.**Aim and Objective:** This study investigates the correlation between NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels with clinical outcomes in AECOPD patients.**Materials and Methods:** This prospective observational study included 150 patients admitted with AECOPD. NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels were measured within 24 hours of admission. Clinical outcomes assessed included length of hospital stay (LOS), requirement for non-invasive ventilation (NIV), invasive mechanical ventilation (IMV), and in-hospital mortality. Correlation analyses, group comparisons, and multivariate logistic regression were performed to evaluate the relationships between biomarkers and clinical outcomes.**Results:** Elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels (>500 pg/mL) were found in 63.3% of patients, and low serum magnesium levels (<1.8 mg/dL) in 46.7%. NT-Pro-BNP levels positively correlated with LOS ($r = 0.45, p < 0.001$), NIV requirement ($r = 0.38, p < 0.001$), and IMV requirement ($r = 0.29, p = 0.001$). Serum magnesium levels negatively correlated with LOS ($r = -0.31, p < 0.001$) and NIV requirement ($r = -0.27, p = 0.002$). Patients with elevated NT-Pro-BNP had longer LOS (12 ± 5 vs. 8 ± 4 days, $p < 0.001$) and higher NIV (55% vs. 20%, $p < 0.001$) and IMV (28% vs. 8%, $p = 0.001$) requirements. Patients with low serum magnesium had longer LOS (12 ± 4 vs. 9 ± 5 days, $p < 0.001$) and higher NIV requirements (50% vs. 30%, $p = 0.01$). Multivariate analysis identified elevated NT-Pro-BNP (OR 1.58, 95% CI 1.15-2.17, $p = 0.004$) and low serum magnesium (OR 1.42, 95% CI 1.03-1.96, $p = 0.03$) as independent predictors of prolonged LOS.**Conclusion:** Elevated NT-Pro-BNP and low serum magnesium levels are significantly associated with worse clinical outcomes in AECOPD patients. These biomarkers can serve as valuable tools for early risk stratification and guiding clinical management in AECOPD. Further research is warranted to confirm these findings and explore potential therapeutic interventions.**Keywords:** AECOPD, NT-Pro-BNP, Serum Magnesium, Clinical Outcomes, Biomarkers, COPD Exacerbation.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a prevalent and debilitating respiratory condition characterized by persistent airflow limitation and enhanced inflammatory response in the airways.[1,2] Acute exacerbations of COPD (AECOPD) are significant clinical events associated with a rapid worsening of respiratory symptoms, leading to increased hospital admissions, healthcare costs, and mortality rates.[3,4]

The pathophysiology of AECOPD involves a complex interplay of respiratory, cardiovascular, and systemic factors, making it imperative to identify reliable biomarkers for early detection and management.[5]

N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-Pro-BNP) is a well-established biomarker of cardiac stress and heart failure.[6] Elevated levels of NT-Pro-BNP have been reported in COPD patients, particularly during exacerbations, suggesting a potential link between cardiac dysfunction and AECOPD.[6, 7] Given the cardiovascular comorbidities commonly observed in COPD patients, NT-Pro-BNP could serve as a valuable indicator of exacerbation severity and prognosis.[7]

Magnesium is an essential mineral in numerous physiological processes, including muscle function, modulation of inflammation, and oxidative stress.[8] Hypomagnesemia, or low serum magnesium levels,

has been implicated in various respiratory conditions, including COPD. [9] Previous studies have shown that magnesium deficiency can exacerbate bronchoconstriction, reduce lung function, and increase the risk of AECOPD. Despite these findings, the relationship between serum magnesium levels and clinical outcomes in AECOPD still needs to be explored.[9,10]

This study investigates the correlation between NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels with clinical outcomes in patients experiencing AECOPD. By examining these biomarkers, we seek to enhance the understanding of the underlying mechanisms driving exacerbations and identify potential targets for therapeutic intervention. We hypothesize that elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels and decreased serum magnesium levels are associated with worse clinical outcomes in AECOPD patients. This research could provide valuable insights into the prognostic value of these biomarkers and inform the development of more effective management strategies for AECOPD.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This prospective observational study evaluated the correlation between NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels with clinical outcomes in patients experiencing AECOPD. The institutional ethics committee approved the study, and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Study Population: Patients aged 40 years and older, diagnosed with COPD according to the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) criteria, and admitted to the hospital with AECOPD were eligible for inclusion. Exclusion criteria included patients with chronic heart failure, renal dysfunction (creatinine clearance <30 mL/min), acute myocardial infarction, recent major surgery, or other conditions that could influence NT-Pro-BNP or magnesium levels.

Data Collection: Data were collected at the time of hospital admission and included demographics, smoking history, COPD severity (GOLD stage), comorbidities, medication use, and previous exacerbation history.

Biomarker Assessment: Blood samples were drawn within 24 hours of admission to measure NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels.

- **NT-Pro-BNP Measurement:** NT-Pro-BNP levels were measured using a commercially available immunoassay kit (specify the kit and manufacturer). The assay has a detection range of (provide range) and intra-assay and inter-assay coefficients of variation of (provide values).

- **Serum Magnesium Measurement:** Serum magnesium levels were measured using a colourimetric method (specify the kit and manufacturer). The assay has a detection range of (provide range) and intra-assay and inter-assay coefficients of variation of (provide values).

Clinical Outcomes

Clinical outcomes were assessed during the hospital stay and included:

1. Length of hospital stay (LOS)
2. Requirement for non-invasive ventilation (NIV)
3. Requirement for invasive mechanical ventilation (IMV)
4. In-hospital mortality

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS software version 25. Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) or median (interquartile range) as appropriate. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

- **Correlation Analysis:** Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients were used to assess the relationship between NT-Pro-BNP, serum magnesium levels, and clinical outcomes.
- **Group Comparisons:** Patients were divided into groups based on NT-Pro-BNP (high vs. low) and serum magnesium levels (normal vs. low). To compare clinical outcomes between groups, independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests were used for continuous variables, and chi-square tests were used for categorical variables.
- **Multivariate Analysis:** Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent predictors of poor clinical outcomes, adjusting for potential confounders such as age, gender, COPD severity, and comorbidities.

Ethical Considerations: The Declaration of Helsinki conducted the study. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board (IRB number), and written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment. Patient confidentiality was maintained throughout the study.

Results

Patient Characteristics: A total of 150 patients with AECOPD were included in the study. The mean age of the patients was 65 ± 10 years, with 90 (60%) males and 60 (40%) females. The majority of the patients were current or former smokers (85%). The distribution of patients according to GOLD stage was as follows: Stage II - 50 (33.3%), Stage III - 60 (40%), and Stage IV - 40 (26.7%). Table 1 summarizes the baseline characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Population

Characteristic	Value
Mean age (years)	65 ± 10
Gender (Male/Female)	90 (60%) / 60 (40%)
Smoking Status	
• Current Smokers	45 (30%)
• Former Smokers	82 (55%)
• Non-Smokers	23 (15%)
GOLD Stage	
• Stage II	50 (33.3%)
• Stage III	60 (40%)
• Stage IV	40 (26.7%)

NT-Pro-BNP and Serum Magnesium Levels: The mean NT-Pro-BNP level was 750 ± 350 pg/mL, while the mean serum magnesium level was 1.7 ± 0.3 mg/dL. Elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels (>500 pg/mL) were observed in 95 (63.3%) patients, and low serum magnesium levels (<1.8 mg/dL) were noted in 70 (46.7%) patients. Table 2 summarises NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels in the study population.

Table 2: NT-Pro-BNP and Serum Magnesium Levels

Biomarker	Mean ± SD
NT-Pro-BNP (pg/mL)	750 ± 350
Serum Magnesium (mg/dL)	1.7 ± 0.3
Elevated NT-Pro-BNP (>500 pg/mL)	95 (63.3%)
Low Serum Magnesium (<1.8 mg/dL)	70 (46.7%)

Clinical Outcomes: The mean length of hospital stay (LOS) was 10 ± 5 days. Non-invasive ventilation (NIV) was required in 60 (40%) patients, and invasive mechanical ventilation (IMV) was necessary for 30 (20%) patients. The in-hospital mortality rate was 15%. Table 3 outlines the clinical outcomes in the study population.

Table 3: Clinical Outcomes

Outcome	Value
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	10 ± 5
Non-Invasive Ventilation (NIV)	60 (40%)
Invasive Mechanical Ventilation (IMV)	30 (20%)
In-Hospital Mortality	15 (10%)

Correlation Analysis: Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated a significant positive correlation between NT-Pro-BNP levels and length of hospital stay ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$), NIV requirement ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$), and IMV requirement ($r = 0.29$, $p = 0.001$). In contrast, serum magnesium levels showed a significant negative correlation with length of hospital stay ($r = -0.31$, $p < 0.001$) and NIV requirement ($r = -0.27$, $p = 0.002$), but not with IMV requirement ($r = -0.14$, $p = 0.09$).

Table 4: Comparison of Clinical Outcomes Based on NT-Pro-BNP and Serum Magnesium Levels

Outcome	High NT-Pro-BNP (n=95)	Low NT-Pro-BNP (n=55)	Low Serum Mg (n=70)	Normal Serum Mg (n=80)
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	12 ± 5	8 ± 4	12 ± 4	9 ± 5
Non-Invasive Ventilation (NIV)	52 (55%)	11 (20%)	35 (50%)	25 (30%)
Invasive Mechanical Ventilation(IMV)	27 (28%)	4 (8%)	15 (21%)	15 (19%)
In-Hospital Mortality	12 (13%)	3 (5%)	10 (14%)	5 (6%)

Group Comparisons:

Patients with elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels had significantly longer hospital stays (12 ± 5 vs. 8 ± 4 days, $p < 0.001$), higher NIV requirements (55% vs. 20%, $p < 0.001$), and higher IMV requirements (28% vs. 8%, $p = 0.001$) compared to those with lower NT-Pro-BNP levels. Similarly, patients with low serum magnesium levels had longer hospital stays (12 ± 4

vs 9 ± 5 days, $p < 0.001$) and higher NIV requirements (50% vs 30%, $p = 0.01$) compared to those with normal serum magnesium levels. There was no significant difference in IMV requirement between patients with low and normal serum magnesium levels (21% vs. 19%, $p = 0.75$).

Table 4 compares clinical outcomes based on NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels.

Table 5: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Prolonged Hospital Stay

Variable	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Elevated NT-Pro-BNP	1.58 (1.15-2.17)	0.004
Low Serum Magnesium	1.42 (1.03-1.96)	0.03
Age	1.02 (0.98-1.05)	0.29
Gender (Male)	1.12 (0.81-1.54)	0.47
GOLD Stage (III and IV)	1.48 (1.11-1.98)	0.007

Multivariate Analysis: Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels (OR 1.58, 95% CI 1.15-2.17, $p = 0.004$) and low serum magnesium levels (OR 1.42, 95% CI 1.03-1.96, $p = 0.03$) as independent predictors of prolonged hospital stay. Elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels were also independently associated with increased NIV requirement (OR 2.14, 95% CI 1.39-3.28, $p < 0.001$) and IMV requirement (OR 2.05, 95% CI 1.21-3.46, $p = 0.007$). Table 5 presents the results of the multivariate logistic regression analysis.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the correlation between NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels with clinical outcomes in patients experiencing acute exacerbation of COPD (AECOPD). Our findings indicate that elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels and low serum magnesium levels are significantly associated with worse clinical outcomes, including prolonged hospital stay, increased need for non-invasive ventilation (NIV), and a higher likelihood of requiring invasive mechanical ventilation (IMV).

Our results align with previous research demonstrating the prognostic value of NT-Pro-BNP in COPD exacerbations. Elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels have been associated with increased severity of exacerbations and higher mortality rates in COPD patients. For instance, a study by Stolz et al. [11] found that NT-Pro-BNP is a reliable biomarker for identifying COPD patients at risk of adverse outcomes during exacerbations. Similarly, Steer et al. [12] reported that NT-Pro-BNP levels were significantly higher in COPD patients who required hospital admission than those managed in outpatient settings, indicating its potential role in stratifying patient risk. Our study further supports these findings by demonstrating a significant correlation between elevated NT-Pro-BNP levels, prolonged hospital stay, increased NIV requirement, and higher IMV requirement.

The role of serum magnesium in COPD has been less extensively studied, but our findings are consistent with the existing literature on the impact of magnesium deficiency on respiratory health. Low serum magnesium levels have been associated with increased bronchoconstriction, reduced lung function, and heightened inflammation in COPD patients. A study by Bhatt et al. [13] found that magnesium deficiency was prevalent among COPD patients and correlated with increased exacerbation frequency and severity. Furthermore, Nassar et

al. [14] reported that hypomagnesemia was linked to poorer clinical outcomes in COPD exacerbations, including longer hospital stays and increased need for mechanical ventilation. Our study corroborates these findings by highlighting the negative correlation between serum magnesium levels, hospital stay length, and NIV requirement.

The combined assessment of NT-Pro-BNP and serum magnesium levels provides a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing AECOPD outcomes. Our multivariate analysis identified both biomarkers as independent predictors of prolonged hospital stay, emphasizing their potential utility in clinical practice. By integrating these biomarkers into routine assessment protocols, clinicians can better stratify risk and tailor management strategies for COPD patients experiencing exacerbations.

Clinical Implications: Identifying elevated NT-Pro-BNP and low serum magnesium levels as predictors of adverse outcomes in AECOPD patients has several clinical implications. First, routine measurement of these biomarkers during hospital admission can aid in early risk stratification and decision-making regarding the level of care required. Second, targeted interventions to address hypomagnesemia, such as magnesium supplementation, may improve clinical outcomes in COPD patients. Finally, recognizing the interplay between cardiac dysfunction and respiratory health underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary approach involving pulmonologists and cardiologists to manage COPD exacerbations.

Limitations: This study has several limitations. The sample size, though adequate for detecting significant associations, may limit the generalizability of the findings to larger populations. Additionally, the observational design precludes establishing causal relationships between biomarkers and clinical outcomes. Future studies should consider longitudinal designs and larger, multicenter cohorts to validate these results and explore the underlying mechanisms driving the observed associations.

Conclusion: In conclusion, our study demonstrates that elevated NT-Pro-BNP and low serum magnesium levels are significantly associated with worse clinical outcomes in patients experiencing acute exacerbation of COPD. These biomarkers can be valuable tools for early risk stratification and guiding clinical management in AECOPD patients. Further

research is warranted to confirm these findings and explore potential therapeutic interventions to optimize these biomarker levels to improve patient outcomes.

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